
Perception of Youths on the Value of Electronic-Based Communication in Provision of Security in Nigeria

Justina Nwadiuto Chukwuebuka-Nwosu & Chinwe Okpoko

Department of Mass Communication,
University of Nigeria Nsukka

Email: jirebus@gmail.com; chinwe.okpoko@unn.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

The paper was an empirical study on how the youths perceived the value of electronic-based communication in provision of security in Nigeria. Three research questions guided the study. A survey research design was used for the study. Population of the study comprised of 1,158 youths studying mass communication in a polytechnic in Anambra State of Nigeria. A random sampling technique was used in selection of 320 youths. The instrument used for data collection was Perception Assessment on Value of Electronic-based Communication on Security (PAVECS) which is a face validated questionnaire made of 30 items. The Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient of the instrument was 0.87. Mean was used in the data analysis for answering the research questions. Result obtained showed that youths have positive perception on the use of electronic-based communication devices for security purpose; and their perception on the value of telecommunication devices and Internet/social media in carrying out activities pertaining to security was positive. It was concluded that Nigeria youths can contribute towards provision of security by making adequate use of electronic-based communication. Recommendations made in the paper include that ignorant youths should be enlighten on the technological value of electronic-based communication in provision of security.

Keywords: Perception, youths, electronic-based communication, security, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is known as a developing nation. For Nigeria to match towards becoming a developed nation, provision of security is very essential. Nwosu, Amechi, Chukwulobe and Chijioke (2014) asserted that national security is a situation whereby inhuman acts and social vices such as murder, robbery, kidnapping, stealing, prostitution and others are prevented or avoided for decent, pleasant and comfortable living in a nation. Security is essential in Nigeria, just as in any nation, because it is concerned with good and healthy state of the body and mind as well as safe guarding of properties. Unfortunately, there is news of insecurity in Nigeria as can be evidenced in existence of

emotional and physical injury, armed-robbery, kidnapping and murder. In Nigeria, one of the factors that bring about insecurity is massive unemployment of the youths (Okoli & Nwosu, 2021). Unemployment is a bad condition for it leads to existence of social vices like prostitution, duping, kidnapping, robbery and killing which affect national development (Ezeife & Amechi, 2021). Based on the ill effect of insecurity in human and national development, efforts towards provision of security in Nigeria is very paramount.

Provision of security in Nigeria can be through effective communication. Communication deals with generation, transmission and reception of information and knowledge. Orji (2010) asserted that communication is the process by which people exchange information or express their thought and feeling; it can be done through signal, touch, noise, etc. It is an axiom that the essence of communication is provision and acquisition of information and knowledge for carrying out activities in human society. Communication for provision of security in this modern era can require the application of electronics. Electronics is concerned with the passage of electricity through semiconductor devices. Communication that involves use of electricity has given rise to electronic-based communication. Electronic-based communication is a communication that employs electronics and it pertains to information and communication technology (ICT). Electronic-based communication is a form of communication that involves the use of electronic technology, which is concerned with production of systems like computer, radio, television, telephone, projector, video machine, photocopier (Nwoye, Okoli & Nwosu, 2021). Nnabuenyi and Nzekwe (2019) asserted that electronics, of which its prominent aspects are telecommunication, computer and information technology, can be used for security purpose.

The use of radio receiver, television and telephone is a kind of electronic-based communication known as telecommunication. It is a form of communication that allows dissemination of information over long distance using electromagnetic wave. Nwosu and Chukwuebuka-Nwosu cited in Obiora and Ezeife (2021) asserted that

the advantage in the use of telecommunication is that it covers a large audience because it addresses the problems of time and space by breaking physical barriers of distance. Computer as an electronic device that can be employed in electronic-based communication has the potential of reducing stress and difficulty in works. Thus, computer is valuable in technological and socio-economic development of human society. Ezeife and Amechi (2021) asserted that computer, as a vital electronic device with technological value, has interesting features that necessitate its great use in this modern era.

Integration of telecommunication and computer gives rise to Information Technology (IT). Information Technology (IT) can be used interchangeable with Information and Communication Technology (ICT), which is a scientific means and act of gathering, storing, processing and transmitting data and information in various ways, especially in electronic forms, for man's wellbeing. A prominent aspect of IT is the Internet. Internet stands for "International Network" and it is the greatest computer network such that people can communicate with one another from any part of the globe any time irrespective of distance. The existence of the Internet has made it possible the use of electronic mail (e-mail) and social media such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Telegram, Zoom, Twitter, and Instagram as a fast and convenient means of communication. Internet has transformed the human world into "global village" where people can easily communicate with one another in multi-media, electronically, from any point in the globe and the technology enhances socio-economic activities (Inyama, cited in Amechi, Chukwulobe & Nwosu, 2016).

The security value of electronic-based communication is so great. Electronic-based communication can serve as a technological means of tackling security challenges in Nigeria through its use in: crime detection and prevention, provision of job, supplying of anti-crime information, acquiring ethical-based education, and avoiding dangerous situation (Chukwuebuka-Nwosu, 2023). Violent crime prevention and detection can be achieved by applying electronic engineering and technology in design and construction of security

devices/systems, creation of job/employment opportunities, dissemination of anti-crime information, and provision of ethical-based education (Nwosu, Ezeilo & Onwughalu, 2015). Okoli and Nwosu (2021) pointed out that electronic-based communication is useful in entrepreneurship which has helped people become creative and innovative in carrying out jobs necessary for fostering security. Nzekwe (2016) noted that Internet enables communicate without travelling, thereby giving forum for minimization or prevention of transportation hazards like traffic congestions, road accidents, lost/damage of property and robbery attack. In the same vien, Nwoye, Okoli and Nwosu, (2021) pointed out that Internet, as a medium for communication, provides security value by enabling people communicate indoor, resulting that there is avoidance of risk and danger associated with outdoor movement/travelling.

On the basis that electronic-based communication is a prominent technology with security value in this modern era, the youths are expected to be familiar with it. The use of electronic-based communication concerns the youths because they are the leaders of tomorrow and agents for culture preservation. The hope for the social, economic and political wellbeing of a nation is the youths (Okoli & Nwosu, 2021). It can be inferred that among the efforts for provision of security in Nigeria is having positive mindset by the youths towards electronic-based communication. On the basis that the position of youths is significant in national development, the focus of this paper is to find out the perception of youths on the value of electronic-based communication in provision of security in Nigeria.

The paper is anchored on the Theory of Technology Determinism. The Theory of Technology Determinism was propounded by Marshall McLuhan in 1962. The theory, as it concerns media technology, pertains to the influence of technology on the society. Technology Determinism theory states that media technology shapes how we as individuals in a society think, feel, act, and how society operates as we move from one technological age to another: Tribal- Literate- Print- Electronic (McLuhan, 1962). The theory of Technology Determinism is

the idea that social change can occur due to existence of technology. The theory stresses that advancement in technology determines the development of the social structure and cultural values. For instance, existence of electronic technology has brought about electronic-based communication in this 21st century. The electronic-based communication has resulted that in this modern society rate of communication using electronics like mobile phone and the Internet is high but that using letter writing on a paper has reduced.

The implication of the Theory of Technology Determinism to this research work is that:

- ❖ The existence of electronic-based communication can serve as a technology employed in provision of security in this modern era.
- ❖ Youths as future leaders of tomorrow need to be well exposed in the knowledge and skills pertaining to use of electronic-based communication in provision of security.

Statement of the Problem

In this 21st century, electronic technology has brought about the use of various electronic devices in the act of communication. Thus, in this 21st century electronic-based communication is greatly employed in human endeavours. Electronic-based communication can be employed by the youths for development in Nigeria. The youth can employ electronic-based communication in area of security to ensure development in Nigeria. To do that, the youths need to perceive electronic-based communication as a valuable technology. On that basis, the research work is face with the problem of finding out the perception of youths on the value of electronic-based communication in provision of security in Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study was to find out the perception of youths on the value of electronic-based communication in provision of security in Nigeria. Specifically, this study was embarked upon to ascertain if the youths:

- Make use of electronic-based communication devices for security purpose.
- Perceive the use of telecommunication devices valuable in provision of security.
- Perceive the use of Internet/social media valuable in provision of security.

Research Questions

To guide the study, the following research questions were formulated:

1. Do the youths make use of electronic-based communication devices for security purpose?
2. Do the youths perceive the use of telecommunication devices valuable in provision of security?
3. Do the youths perceive the use of Internet/social media valuable in provision of security?

METHOD

The research design for this study was survey. The survey structure was used because the research work dealt on the views of the youths on the use and effect electronic-based communication devices. Population of the study comprised of 1,158 youths studying Mass Communication in a Federal Polytechnic in Anambra State of Nigeria. A random sampling technique was used in selection of a sample size of three hundred and twenty (320) youths obtained from the four classes/levels in the Mass Communication Department of the Polytechnic. The instrument used for data collection was Perception Assessment on Value of Electronic-based Communication on Security (PAVECS) which is a questionnaire developed by the researcher. The PAVECS consists of three sections. Each section has ten (10) items specifically meant to provide answer to each of the three research questions for the study. The instrument (PAVECS) was based on four scales: Very Large Extent, Large Extent, Little Extent, and Very Little Extent. The scoring mode for the scale was such that: Very Large Extent = 4, Large Extent = 3, Little Extent = 2, Very Little Extent = 1. The responses on the items and, hence, the scores obtained were used to assess the perception of the respondents (the youths). Face validity

was established for Perception Assessment on Value of Electronic-based Communication on Security (PAVECS) by two (2) experts in Mass Communication and one (1) expert in Education Measurement and Evaluation. For the determination of the reliability of PAVECS, eighty (80) youths studying Mass Communication in a Federal Polytechnic in Imo state of Nigeria were presented with the validated version of the PAVECS for them to response to. Then, the Cronbach's Modified Kuder-Richardson Formula (Cronbach Alpha) was used to calculate the reliability of the instrument and it was found to be reliable with a Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.87. Data analysis for answering the research questions in the study was done by the use mean. Answer to the research questions was provided such that an item in the PAVECS with mean rating up to 2.50 is taken as positive perception while that below 2.50 is considered as negative perception. Positive or negative perception is a situation in which the use/value of devices for communicating electronically for security purpose is taken to be high or low respectively.

RESULT

The number of the respondents used for data collection was three hundred and twenty ($N = 320$). The data collected for the research questions were analyzed and presented in tables.

Research question 1: Do the youths make use of electronic-based communication devices for security purpose?

Table 1 shows that the mean values of the data obtained from the 320 youths used in the study as regards the use of electronic-based communication devices for security purpose were within 1.70 and 3.55 for the 10 items considered. The mean rating in the use of television, radio receiver, telephone/hand set, face book, whatsapp, telegram, zoom, instagram, twitter and e-mail were 3.20, 2.35, 3.55, 3.45, 3.35, 2.70, 1.70, 2.35, 2.40 and 2.50 respectively. The mean rating in the use of telephone/hand set was the highest value ($\bar{X} = 3.55$) while the mean rating in the use of zoom was the least value ($\bar{X} = 1.70$). The cluster mean rating for all the 10 items was 2.76.

Research question 2: Do the youths perceive the use of telecommunication devices valuable in provision of security?

Table 2 shows that the mean values of the data obtained from the 320 respondents for assessing the youths' perception on the value of telecommunication devices (television, radio receiver, telephone/hand set) in provision of security were within 2.80 and 3.60 for the 10 items considered. The mean rating in the extent of use of telecommunication devices for detecting illegal operations, detecting criminals, arresting criminals, preventing illegal/criminal activities, promoting ethical conducts for security, preventing transportation hazard/risk, avoiding harmful operations, providing education on safety, making people become security conscious and encouraging people report insecure activities were 3.15, 3.50, 2.80, 3.50, 3.10, 2.85, 3.10, 3.20, 3.45, and 3.60 respectively. The mean rating in the extent of use of telecommunication devices for encouraging people report insecure activities was of highest value ($\bar{X} = 3.60$) while that for arresting criminals was the least value ($\bar{X} = 2.80$). The cluster mean rating for all the 10 items was 3.23.

Research question 3: Do the youths perceive the use of Internet/social media valuable in provision of security?

Table 3 reveals that the mean values of the data obtained from the 320 respondents for their perception on the value of Internet/social media in provision of security were within 2.80 and 3.60 for the 10 items considered. The mean rating in the extent of use of Internet/social media for detecting illegal operations, detecting criminals, arresting criminals, preventing illegal/criminal activities, promoting ethical conducts for security, preventing transportation hazard/risk, avoiding harmful operations, providing education on safety, making people become security conscious and encouraging people report insecure activities were 2.80, 3.25, 3.50, 3.00, 3.10, 2.95, 2.85, 3.00, 3.60 and 3.60 respectively. The mean rating in the extent of use of Internet/social media for security conscious and encouraging people report insecure activities were of highest value ($\bar{X} = 3.60$) while that for detecting illegal operations was the least value ($\bar{X} = 2.80$). The cluster mean rating for all the 10 items was 3.17.

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows that the youths have positive perception in the use of majority of the electronic-based communication devices mentioned for security purpose. Among the ten electronic-based communication devices mentioned, it was in the use of zoom, radio receiver, instagram and twitter for security purpose that the youths have negative perception. The issue of positive and negative perception connotes high and low usage respectively of electronic-based communication devices for security purpose. Although there was existence of positive and negative perception in the use of electronic-based communication devices, it can be inferred, from the cluster mean in table 1, that the youths make high (signifying positive perception on the) use of electronic-based communication devices for security purpose. The result obtained from this study is in agreement with the: acknowledgment by Okoli and Nwosu (2021) that electronic-based communication (through entrepreneurship) can be used in fostering security; assertion by Nnabuenyi and Nzekwe (2019) that electronics can be used for security purpose.

Table 2 shows that the youths positively perceive that the use of telecommunication devices is valuable in carrying out all the security activities mentioned. Positive perception is a reflection that the use of telecommunication devices is of high value in provision of security. It can be deduced from the cluster mean in table 2 that the youths perceive the use of telecommunication devices highly valuable in provision of security. The finding of this study is in line with the view of Chukwuebuka-Nwosu (2023) that telecommunication helps in fighting insecurity: with the use of telephone, the law enforcement and security agencies can be notified of criminal operations; through radio and television broadcast and programmes, the masses can be informed and educated to desist from criminal acts.

Table 3 shows that the youths positively perceive that the use of Internet/social media is valuable in executing the ten security activities stated in the study. Positive perception denotes that the use of Internet/social media is of high value in provision of security. From the

cluster mean in table 3, it can be inferred that the youths perceive the use of Internet/social media highly valuable in provision of security. The finding of this study is in agreement with the statement of: Nzekwe (2016) that Internet enables communicate without travelling, resulting to minimization or prevention of transportation hazards like road accidents, lost/damage of property and robbery attack; Nwoye, Okoli and Nwosu, (2021) that Internet provides security value by enabling people communicate indoor, resulting that there is avoidance of risk and danger associated with outdoor movement/travelling; Obiora and Ezeife (2021) that educative information on security can be obtained through social media like Facebook, Telegram, WhatsApp, Twitter, and others.

CONCLUSION

Among the socio-economic move that can help Nigeria become a developed nation is ensuring of adequate security in the nation. To ensure security in the nation, the Nigeria youths need to be greatly involved in the match towards provision of security. At this modern era, Nigeria youths can employ electronics in contributing towards provision of security by making adequate use of electronic-based communication. It was found out in the study that the youths have positive perception on the use of electronic-based communication devices for security purpose. Such perception denotes that the youths, for security purpose, make high use of majority of electronic-based communication devices/facilities like television, telephone, handset, facebook, whatsapp, telegram, and e-mail. The study also found out that the youths have positive perception on ie placed high value in the use of telecommunication devices and Internet/social media in carrying out activities pertaining to provision of security.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that:

1. Well-to-do individuals, organizations and government should provide funds and facilities that will encourage the youths use electronic devices for provision of security.

2. Electric power providers should provide sufficient electrical energy to enable the youths effectively power devices utilized in electronic-based communication.
3. Intellectuals and mass media should enlighten ignorant youths on the technological value of electronic-based communication in provision of security.
4. Ethical conducts should be valued and maintained by the Nigerian youths in the use of electronic devices for communication.

REFERENCES

- Amechi, M.C., Chukwulobe, E.E. & Nwosu, F.C. (2016). Value of silicon in the development of electronic technology for socio-economic wellbeing of human society. *International Journal of Research and Advancement in Engineering Science*, 6 (1), 88 – 92.
- Chukwuebuka-Nwosu, J.N. (2023). *Technological value of electronic-based communication in tackling security challenges in Nigeria*. A seminar paper written and presented in the Department of Mass Communication, University of Nigeria Nsukka.
- Ezeife, J.E & Amechi, M.C. (2021) Usefulness of computer in promotion of entrepreneurship needed for development in Nigeria. *Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship*, 1 (1), 56 - 61.
- McLuhan, M. (1962). *The Gutenberg galaxy: the making of typographic man*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press.
- Nnabuenyi, H.O. & Nzekwe, F.N. (2019). The use of semiconductor in electronics in ensuring quality in science and technology. *Knowledge Review*, 38 (1), 57 – 63.
- Nwosu, F.C., Amechi, M.C, Chukwulobe, E.E. & Chijioke, A.I. (2014). Value of electronics and computer in fostering national security for sustainable development in Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Engineering*, 11 (1) 38 - 44.
- Nwosu, F. C., Ezeilo, C. J. & Onwughalu, M. K. (2015). Impact of electronic engineering and technology in curbing violent crime for sustainable development. *International Bi-lingual Journal of Anti-Corruption, Law, Humanities, Social Sciences and Development Studies*, 6(1), 28 – 34.

- Nwoye, A.N., Okoli, G.C. & Nwosu, F.C. (2021). *Electronic-based communication as a means of management of education in covid-19 era*. Paper presented during the 2nd bi-annual state conference of Science Teachers' Association of Nigeria, Anambra State branch held at Federal Science and Technical College Awka from 8th – 9th December.
- Nzekwe, F.N. (2016). Value of electronic technology in fostering security in human environment. *International Journal of Advancement in Development Studies*, 11 (1) 141 – 144.
- Obiora, J.U. & Ezeife, J.E. (2021). Application of telecommunication and computer in provision of security in post covid-19 era in Nigeria. *International Journal of Applied Science Research*, 1, 140 – 145.
- Okoli, G.C. & Nwosu, F.C. (2021). Potentials of electronics in human development of Nigerian youths towards entrepreneurship. *Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship*, 1 (1), 12 - 17.
- Orji, M.C. (2010). Communication in the planning of the family finance. *International Bi-lingual Journal of Anti-Corruption, Law, Humanities, Social Sciences and Development Studies*, 1 (2), 157 – 162.

Appendix

Table 1: Use of electronic-based communication devices for security purpose

S/N	Items	(N = 320) \bar{X}	Decision
1	Television	3.20	Positive perception
2	Radio receiver	2.35	Negative perception
3	Telephone/hand set	3.55	Positive perception
4	Face book	3.45	Positive perception
5	WhatsApp	3.35	Positive perception
6	Telegram	2.70	Positive perception
7	Zoom	1.70	Negative perception
8	Instagram	2.35	Negative perception
9	Twitter	2.40	Negative perception
10	e-mail	2.50	Positive perception
	Cluster mean	2.76	Positive perception

Table 2: Perception on the value of telecommunication devices in provision of security

S/N	Items	(N = 320) \bar{X}	Decision
1	Detecting illegal operations	3.15	Positive perception
2	Detecting criminals	3.50	Positive perception
3	Arresting criminals	2.80	Positive perception
4	Preventing illegal/criminal activities	3.50	Positive perception
5	Promoting ethical conducts for security	3.10	Positive perception
6	Preventing transportation hazard/risk	2.88	Positive perception
7	Avoiding harmful operations	3.10	Positive perception
8	Providing education on safety	3.20	Positive perception
9	Making people become security conscious	3.45	Positive perception
10	Encouraging people report insecure activities	3.60	Positive perception
	Cluster mean	3.23	Positive perception

Table 3: Perception on the value of Internet/social media in provision of security

S/N	Items	(N = 320) \bar{X}	Decision
1	Detecting illegal operations	2.80	Positive perception
2	Detecting criminals	3.25	Positive perception
3	Arresting criminals	3.50	Positive perception
4	Preventing illegal/criminal activities	3.00	Positive perception
5	Promoting ethical conducts for security	3.10	Positive perception
6	Preventing transportation hazard/risk	2.95	Positive perception
7	Avoiding harmful operations	2.85	Positive perception
8	Providing education on safety	3.00	Positive perception

Perception of Youths on the Value of Electronic-Based Communication in Provision of Security in Nigeria

9	Making people become security conscious	3.60	Positive perception
10	Encouraging people report insecure activities	3.60	Positive perception
Cluster mean		3.17	Positive perception

Perception Assessment on Value of Electronic-based Communication on Security (PAVECS)

Department of Mass Communication
University of Nigeria Nsukka
26th January, 2024.

Dear Respondent,

The Researcher is embarking on a research work on 'Perception of Youths on the Value of Electronic-based Communication in Provision of Security in Nigeria'. Your responses will be treated confidentially since the research is for academic purpose. Please, sincerely indicate your feeling by ticking '✓' in any of the options in each item of the questionnaire. The options are: very large extent=VLE; large extent=LE; small extent=SE; very small extent=VSE

Thanks

Chukwuebuka-Nwosu, J.N. (Mrs)
(Researcher)

Section A

For security value, I make use of:

S/No	Items	VLE	LE	SE	VSE
1.	Television to a				
2.	Radio receiver to a				
3.	Telephone/hand set to a				
4.	Face book to a				
5.	WhatsApp to a				
6.	Telegram to a				
7.	Zoom to a				
8.	Instagram to a				
9.	Twitter to a				

10.	e-mail				
-----	--------	--	--	--	--

Section B

The use of telecommunication devices (television, radio, telephone) is valuable in:

S/No	Items	VLE	LE	SE	VSE
1.	Detecting illegal operations to a				
2.	Detecting criminals to a				
3.	Arresting criminals to a				
4.	Preventing illegal/criminal activities to a				
5.	Promoting ethical conducts for security to a				
6.	Preventing transportation hazards/risks to a				
7.	Avoiding harmful operations to a				
8.	Providing education on safety to a				
9.	Making people become security conscious to a				
10.	Encouraging people report insecure activities to a				

Section C

The use of Internet/social media (e-mail, face book, WhatsApps, etc) is valuable in:

S/No	Items	VLE	LE	SE	VSE
1.	Detecting illegal operations to a				
2.	Detecting criminals to a				
3.	Arresting criminals to a				
4.	Preventing illegal/criminal activities to a				
5.	Promoting ethical conducts for security to a				
6.	Preventing transportation hazards/risks to a				
7.	Avoiding harmful operations to a				
8.	Providing education on safety to a				
9.	Making people become security conscious to a				
10.	Encouraging people report insecure activities to a				